

Research Questionnaire

Program Doktor Ilmu Manajemen

Universitas Brawijaya

To
Dear. Sir/Madam
in place.

Yours faithfully,

Along with this letter, I:

Name/NIM: Ni Nyoman Suliati (NIM: 237020200111009).

Status: Doctoral Program Student of Management Science, Faculty of Economics and Business,
Brawijaya University

On this occasion, I really hope for your willingness to fill out the attached questionnaire related to the research I am conducting. The questionnaire that you have filled out will be used as data in my research entitled:

“Transformational Leadership and Innovative Work Behavior: The Sequential Mediating Role of Knowledge Sharing and Creative Self-Efficacy

Your participation in filling out the questionnaire is very meaningful to me. I hope that you will be willing to provide answers according to the actual conditions. All data and information that you provide in the questionnaire will be kept confidential and will only be used for academic purposes related to this research. Thank you.

Researcher,

Ni Nyoman Suliati

I. Respondent Identity

Hotel Name :

Respondent's Name :

Age :

Gender : Male Female

Provincial Origin : Bali Outside Bali

Current Position :

Last education : SMA Diploma S1 S2

Working period : 3 years 4-5 years >5 years

II. Instructions for Completing the Questionnaire Answers

Please answer the following questions by marking (X) in one of the columns provided.

Give your opinion according to the following criteria:

Cross (X) number 1 if you Strongly Disagree (SD)

Cross (X) number 2 if you Disagree (DA)

Cross (X) number 3 if you Quite Agree (QA)

Cross (X) number 4 if you Agree (A)

Cross (X) number 5 if you Strongly Agree (SA)

III. List of Statements

1. *Transformational Leadership*

No	Statement Items	Measurement Scale				
		SD	DA	QA	A	SA
A.	Idealized influence					
1.	The leader makes employees feel proud to be associated with him/her					
2.	The leader encourages employees to be more creative					
B.	Inspirational motivation					
3.	The leader articulates important goals in a clear and simple manner					
4.	The leader inspires employees to view difficult problems from a new perspective					
C.	Intellectual stimulation					
5.	The leader encourages employees to reconsider ideas they once thought were perfect					
6.	The leader challenges employees to re-evaluate their assumptions and previously accepted ideas					
D.	Individualized consideration					
7.	The leader gives praise when employees perform well					
8.	The leader gives personal attention to employees when they need it					

2. Knowledge Sharing

No	Statement Items	Measurement Scale				
		SD	DA	QA	A	SA
A.	Knowledge Donating					
1.	When I learn something new, I share it with my colleagues					
2.	I share the information I have with my colleagues					
B.	Knowledge collecting					
3.	I ask my colleagues about their expertise when I need to learn something					
4.	When a colleague is skilled at something, I ask them to teach me how to do it					

3. Creative Self-Efficacy

No	Statement Items	Measurement Scale				
		SD	DA	QA	A	SA
Confidence in generating new ideas						
1.	I believe I am good at generating new ideas					
Confidence in solving problems creatively						
2.	I am confident in my ability to solve problems creatively					
Confidence in developing other people's ideas						
3.	I have a talent for developing other people's ideas					
Confidence in finding creative ways to solve problems						
4.	I am good at finding creative ways to solve problems					

4. Innovative Work Behavior

No	Statement Items	Measurement Scale				
		SD	DA	QA	A	SA
A.	Idea Exploration					
1.	Pay attention to issues that are not part of the daily work					
2.	Wondering how things can be improved					
B.	Idea Generation					
3.	Looking for new working methods					
4.	Generating original solutions to problems					
5.	Finding new approaches to carrying out tasks					
C.	Idea Championing					
6.	Make organizational members enthusiastic about innovative ideas					
7.	Trying to convince people to support an innovative idea					
8.	Systematically introduce innovative ideas into work practices					
D.	Idea Implementation					
9.	Contribute to the implementation of new ideas					
10.	Trying to develop new things					